

A doomed couple of diamond with terahertz technology: hyperfine quality discrimination and complex dielectric responses of diamond in terahertz broadband

Yuting Zheng^{a,b}, Rui Zhang^c, Xiaodong Chen^c, Peter Hing^b, Jinlong Liu^a, Junjun Wei^a,
Chengming Li^{a,*}, Haitao Ye^{b,*}

- a. Institute for Advanced Materials and Technology, University of Science and Technology Beijing, Beijing 100083, PR China.
- b. School of Engineering, University of Leicester, Leicester, LE1 7RH, UK
- c. School of Electronic Engineering and Computer Science, Queen Mary University of London, London, E1 4FZ, UK.

E-mail address: nevermoreKEVIN@163.com (Yuting Zheng)

*Corresponding author

E-mail address: chengmli@mater.ustb.edu.cn (Chengming Li) TEL: +(86)010 62332390

haitao.ye@leicester.ac.uk (Haitao Ye) TEL: +44(0)1162297377

Abstract:

Using terahertz (THz) time domain spectroscopy in broadband frequency range (0.1–7 THz), we demonstrate experimentally, for the first time, the fingerprint absorption peaks **in low and intermediate wavebands** as well as the complex dielectric response trends in full waveband, on **designedly synthesized and processed polycrystalline and single crystal diamonds** with systematic quality-difference. The two absorption responses within the low-frequency band, in which the atomic vibration is materials-independent, as well as the one in the intermediate frequency range, are attributed to the sp^2 phonon vibration modes of as-grown graphitic phases and/or cleavage defects. Regarding the complex dielectric responses of diamond in THz waveband, scattering effect resulting from the extended grain boundaries associated with concomitant pores (and/or crystal cleavage faults), as well as intrinsic lattice absorption and the charge polarization due to increased sp^2 impurities, have been taken into account. The defect size comparable with the wavelength is also found to play a decisive effect on the loss limits at high-frequency EMW. In particular, the drastic reduction of permittivity is found as the frequency approaches intermediate and high-frequency wavebands. These findings are expected to promote not only ultra-sensitive quality diagnose for diamond but verification of an ideal transmission material for THz waveband applications.

Introduction

The technology age of THz frequency, which is generally defined as the electromagnetic waves (EMW) in the range of 0.1–10 THz, is coming with tremendous features and astonishing applications in various fields of science [1,2]. This huge bandwidth of THz waves will enable us to achieve higher data-rates for the communication application, especially in the critical areas such as satellite transmission, radio astronomy or defence in complex and extreme operational environments; or the THz high-power free electron laser (THz-FEL), which allows us to realize future deeper research on biology and physics [3-5]. Likewise, in practice, controlled thermonuclear fusion cannot operate without injection of high frequency EMW for mitigating magneto-hydrodynamic instability which occurs in the plasma [6]. In those extreme conditions, either for the outer space or the high-energy injection in fusion reactor, or FEL, a millimetre (MM) and submillimetre (sub-MM) waves transparent window with high thermal conductivity, excellent comprehensive mechanical performance and low dielectric losses is mandatory [6,7]. Further, in return, THz technology will be the key milestone not only for the future wireless communication but also the non-destructive ultra-sensitive detection method for probing and/or diagnostics of materials [8-10]. Just because the THz frequency provides direct information access to vibrational modes of the phase, its spectroscopy is strongly believed to be a new and reliable analytical spectroscopic technology with higher sensitivity (resolution) of variable excitation modes of materials, especially for solids [10-13]. Overall, because of this ultra-sensitivity in THz waveband, it thus can be predicted that unsatisfied properties/quality and insufficient processing accuracy cause unavoidable dielectric loss of materials. This will limit the use of current technologies for those mentioned advanced THz-wave applications [2].

Currently only the chemical vapour deposition (CVD) diamond has shown satisfactory characteristics and its losses are still far in excess of the theoretical limit [14]. Indeed, diamond has been widely recognized as an ultra-limit functional material owing to its numerous excellent intrinsic properties such as wide bandgap, low thermal expansion, supreme thermal conductivity, high lattice Debye temperature and sound velocity, as well as ideal crystal symmetry. These intrinsic properties of diamond play a decisive effect on loss limits at high-frequency EMW [15,16]. These features result in not only extremely low phonon absorption at THz waveband but service satisfaction in complex conditions. Exhilaratingly, the quality and dimensions of CVD diamonds has been significantly progressed in recent decades, e.g., microwave plasma (MP)-CVD or DC arc-jet plasma CVD all have been successfully employed for synthesising large-size high-quality polycrystalline diamond (PCD) and single crystal diamond (SCD) [17,18]. Remarkably, the CVD diamonds exhibit very low dielectric loss than any other crystal known today and shows also a low temperature coefficient from microwave (MW) to THz frequency [19]. Yamada, et al [20] have presented the outstanding dielectric properties of polished clone mosaic

SCD at D (0.11-0.17 THz) band and found that rough surface and sp^2 phase as well as cracks were the main causes of power loss of EMW. Liu and Grain [21,22] reported that defects and sp^2 conduction are the reasons of dielectric loss at sub-MM wavelength although the use of PCDs exhibited lowest loss performance. These factors of EMW attenuation that also have been confirmed by Heidinger and Polyakov [14,23]. Meanwhile, the feasibilities of CVD diamond window prototype in nuclear fusion system have been conducted by Mazzocchi and Scherer [24,25]. Further, Yamamoto, et al. [26] carried out the dielectric loss of CVD diamond in the range up to 2.2 THz by THz time-domain spectroscopy (THz-TDS) and predictably suggested that some other dielectric response might be presented above 2.5 THz. Unceasingly, the transmission properties of a PCD wafer in wider THz range and application on FEL was preliminarily studied by Kubarev [27,28].

However, **most** of **the** researchers just investigated the dielectric losses of CVD diamonds in limit waveband within 1 THz, and very few scholars studied the range higher than 2 THz especially concerning the conformation of characteristic absorption of impurity phase for hyperfine quality discrimination. Currently, there is basically **no report** representing the responses of CVD diamonds with systematic quality-difference or defect types in wide THz range. A competent window material and/or ultra-sensitive phase identification for quality control are both vital for advancing THz technology. Therefore, more in-depth study of THz spectroscopy of different diamond films is urgently needed. The effort concerning the responses and/or identifications of different series of CVD diamonds in THz broadband, as shown in Fig.1, are expected to promote vigorously diamond and THz spectroscopy technology for future cutting-edge application.

Fig.1 Schematic of responses of diamond in THz waveband

In this paper, as illustrated in Fig.1, a series of CVD free-standing PCD films with systematically different quality (sp^2 proportion and grain **boundary dimensions**) and an additional series of CVD SCD films with various artificial defects (cleavage types) were radiated by 0.1 – 7 THz waves. The characteristic absorptions and the change trends of complex dielectric constant in this broadband range were obtained. Each series of samples were synthesized designedly to guarantee the uniformity and repeatability based on the systematic quality-difference. And all diamonds were processed into ultra-smooth and insulative surface in order to avoid the dielectric loss

effect of surface roughness and conductive channel of hydrogen-termination [23,25].

Experiment

Four identical $3.5 \times 3.5 \times 0.24$ mm high quality SCD (100) samples were cut from a large grinded CVD diamond mother-crystal, of initial dimensions $7 \text{ mm} \times 7 \text{ mm}$. Homoepitaxial growth was applied on the high-pressure high-temperature (HPHT) diamond substrate at $1000 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 20 h in a **laboratory built** 100 kW DC arc-jet plasma CVD system [29,30]. After pre-polish the mother-crystal by lapping/polishing machine (UNIPOL-802), three of dissected SCD samples were further precisely polished by high-speed 3-dimensional dynamic friction polishing (3D-DFP, Helix) system at a linear speed of 12 m s^{-1} , 35.8 m s^{-1} and 60 m s^{-1} , respectively, corresponding to moderate speed (MS), high speed (HS) and super high speed (SHS). Although the surface of samples was achieved to ultra-smooth (roughness $< 1 \text{ nm}$ in Root-Mean-Square (RMS)), some specific subsurface artificial defects were created purposely, which has been thoroughly investigated in our previous work [31]. One left unpolished (UP) was set as a reference. For the abbreviation, all the SCD samples were labelled as SCD-UP, SCD-MS, SCD-HS and SCD-SHS, respectively.

Meanwhile, a series of $5 \times 5 \times 0.36$ mm PCDs with systematic quality-difference were cut from large free-standing PCD wafers. The PCD wafers were grown using the following identical conditions: MPCVD at $900 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ with an input power of 4.4-4.5 kW, chamber pressure of 4.0-4.5 kPa and a gas flow of H_2 at 300 sccm in a **laboratory built** MPCVD system (2.45 GHz and 6 kW) on silicon wafers. However, for the black (B)-PCD growth, 30 sccm CH_4 was added into the growth chamber, whilst for white (W)-PCDs with different quality, 20, 15 and 10 sccm CH_4 were added, respectively. Owing to the harder smoothing of the surface resulting from the multi-crystal-directions of PCD, SHS polishing process was introduced. Therefore, the abbreviations of PCD series were set based on the quality and CH_4 input flow as well as polishing process, i.e., BPCD-30-SHS, WPCD-20-SHS, WPCD-15-SHS, WPCD-10-SHS, respectively. It should be noted here that the surface roughness of each diamond sample including SCD and PCD was basically the same after 3D-DFP [31].

The quality of diamonds and phase analysis were realized by a high-resolution (HR) Raman spectroscope (HORIBA, LabRAM-HR) with a charge coupled device (CCD, Synapse) and detector measurements under a 532 nm excitation wavelength laser. Meanwhile, the HR optical microscope (OM) in transmission mode is fixed in Raman spectroscopy system. XRD characterization (Rigaku TTR), using $\text{CuK}_{\alpha 1}$ X-ray radiation ($\lambda=1.54056 \text{ nm}$) with an incident angle of 10° , was employed to investigate the multiple crystal-orientations of PCD. A scanning electron microscope (SEM, HITACHI-S4800) and atomic force microscopy (AFM, ASYLUM-RESEARCH HVA220) were used to observe the surface morphologies. Cathodoluminescence imaging (CL, ZEISS-Gemini, Omega-300) was employed to detect the defects, pores and **grain boundaries** (GBs) in the synthesized diamonds. The primary electron acceleration voltage was from 10 to 30 kV and operated at room temperature. The chemical composition at GBs/pores areas of the PCD samples was further characterized by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS, Thermo-Scientific,

ESCALAB-250Xi). In addition, *in-situ* analysis of the gas phase chemistries of the deposition process was performed by using an optical emission spectroscopy (OES-71MS3011). The emission of chemical species from the discharge plasma can certify the variable quality associated with different sp^2 phase content in the series of PCD samples. The THz-TDS setting as shown in Fig.2, was introduced to study the response of diverse diamond samples in 0.1-7 THz frequency range.

Fig.2. Schematic diagram of an advanced THz-TDS system operating in transmission mode

In the schematic diagram of THz-TDS system in Fig.2, the L, P, B stand for flat reflecting mirrors, M represents flat mirrors of delay stage, LS, A, BS, QWP and OM means focusing lenses, attenuators, beam splitter, quarter-wave plate, and off-axis parabolic mirrors, respectively. All the setup components are on a floated table to avoid mechanical vibration during measurements. The THz beam path is marked in blue, and an enclosing box for controlling atmosphere about the sample under test to mitigate the influence of water vapor which causes absorption, is shown by the bold red line. The pulsed titanium-sapphire laser produces femto-second pulses, which are then redirected into separate optical paths by a beam-splitter. The THz emitter is biased low-temperature (LT)-GaAs photoconductive antenna. Its gap size is approximately 0.5 mm which makes the laser beam positioning easier. ZnTe (2 mm thickness is chosen to allow enough interaction length of probe beam and THz wave in the crystal) (110) crystal is used as THz electro-optic detector. Meanwhile, a discrete Fourier-Transform (FT) is then applied to the time-domain response to provide discrete amplitude and phase spectra. The mechanical, optical and electronic components as well as other sources of random and systematic errors introduced from various and estimation procedures are considered; more details can be found in Ref [32]. Meanwhile, the system was calibrated by high-purity silicon, quartz and highly dispersive lithium niobate. The accurate information of thickness determination using the total-variation (TV) technique has been assessed. The accuracy of this TV method is shown to reach $\pm 0.1 \mu\text{m}$ and the thickness result is highly consistent with that of

ultra-precise digital profiler measurements (GUANGLU). For free-standing diamond sample testing, the spectra of each individual sample were obtained without the effect of reference sample.

Results and discussion

Fig.3. Spectroscopy of growth analysis and quality of PCDs with systematical quality difference: a) OES spectroscopy of plasma with variable CH_4 input flow; b) Raman spectroscopy of these PCDs. The upper inset in b) is the XRD pattern of PCD and the below one is the Raman 3D fine illustration of WPCD series

OES *in-situ* plasma diagnostics for different quality PCDs growth is shown in Fig.3(a). The CH (387.2 nm, 431.4 nm) radicals and C_2 (468 nm, 516 nm, 563 nm) species are significantly enhanced by increasing the input content of CH_4 . These two kinds of species were widely accepted as the sources for diamond growth in H_2/CH_4 gas mixtures. The C_2 dimer is thought to be the one important player in the grain growth mechanism for polycrystalline diamond growth [33,34]. It is attributed to enhanced re-nucleation of the growing film, which effectively increases the uniformity over the entire film [35]. Therefore, as shown in Fig.3(b), with the rising of CH_4 addition, from WPCD-10 to WPCD-20, a wide bulge at around 1450 cm^{-1} , which is attributed to the amorphous carbon (*a*-C) and trans-polyacetylene (*t*-PA), arises gradually. Indeed, as shown in Fig.3(a), the excess atomic hydrogen bombardment may be the cause of extensive breaking of the *t*-PA bonds thereby leading to preferential etching of hydrocarbons attached to diamond surfaces. This would allow the C_2 in the plasma to further attach to these surfaces, leading to anisotropic growth of the grains [34]. However, the quality of PCD will be degraded due to the offset effect on preferential etching and the sp^2 phases surviving with more CH_4 addition. This is the reason why the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of sp^3 peak is broadened and sp^2 phases (including disordered sp^2 breathing mode (D band) at $1300\text{-}1350\text{ cm}^{-1}$, C=C bonds of *t*-PA and C-C stretching mode (G band) at 1580 cm^{-1}) related peaks are dominated in the Raman spectra of BPCD-30 [36]. Owing to the internal stress resulting from defects and multi-direction crystal structure shown in the inset XRD pattern of PCD, the diamond sp^3 peak is slightly shifted.

Fig.4. SEM images of surface morphology of as-polished PCD samples: a) WPCD-10-SHS; b) WPCD-15-SHS; c) WPCD-20-SHS; d) BPCD-30-SHS. The inset in each image is the corresponding fine fitted C 1s XPS spectra of grain boundary

In terms of deterioration of PCDs with variable CH_4 addition, quantitative sp^2 contents and visual crystal profile are further displayed. Fig.4 shows the surface images and deconvoluted C 1s XPS spectra of GBs of as-polished PCDs with variable quality. The results of XPS were calibrated before fitting the curves by the adventitious carbon [37]. In addition to the Raman sp^2 related peaks evolution in Fig.3(b), correspondingly, the change of SEM surface morphology and the ratio of sp^3/sp^2 at GBs further indicate that the GB areas are extended apparently and sp^2 graphitic phases are proliferated with the degradation of PCD although the surface roughness of each sample is the same after 3D-DFP process. Owing to the enhanced re-nucleation rate and growth promotion by more contents of C_2 and CH_x radicals in the plasma environment, improved competitive growth of crystal resulted the development of GBs. It is believed that the CH species adhere to the diamond clusters forming an encapsulating layer of *t*-PA phase that prevents the C_2 (or other active carbon species) to attach to the existing diamond clusters without fast enough H etching [34]. The active carbon species like C_2 can re-nucleate new diamond clusters, resulting in new grains granular structure. Namely, more micro-pores and defects appeared along with the GBs formation and thus the diamond film prepared at low CH_4 concentration was of high quality [38]. In the meantime, more sp^2 phases such as graphite or graphene nanoribbon were stored [39]. As shown in the insets of Fig.4, it is observed that the C 1s peak can be mainly deconvoluted into two components at 284.4 and 285.6 eV, which are assigned to sp^2 and sp^3 , respectively [39]. Sequentially, the ratio of sp^3/sp^2 is changed from 3.17 of WPCD-10 to 2.29 of WPCD-15 and then to 2.24 of WPCD-20, and even achieved to 1.07 of BPCD-30.

Fig.5. CL images of subsurface morphology of as-polished PCD samples: a) WPCD-10-SHS; b) BPCD-30-SHS. The inset in each image is the corresponding OM image

Further, Fig.5 supportively shows the CL and OM images of WPCD-10-SHS and BPCD-30-SHS to microscopically present the difference between of high and poor quality PCDs. As illustrated in WPCD-10-SHS, it has large grains and thin GBs without any pores. Thus, its colour in OM is basically transparent which means high quality of crystal. Meanwhile, some multi-direction cleavages are produced by superhigh-speed 3D-DFP in bulk grains [31]. However, for BPCD-30-SHS, because each grain size is about several tens of micron, much smaller than that of WPCD-10-SHS, resulting from the higher re-nucleation rate promoted by more C_2 and CH shown in Fig.3(a), many visible pores associated with lattice disorder (or graphitic phases) in dark contrast colour at GBs as well as less cleavage in crystals are clearly displayed in Fig.5(b). Therefore, sp^2 phases are preferentially proliferated at the grain pores and extended GBs that was detected by XPS and Raman spectroscopy. These differences of BPCD-30-SHS to WPCD-10-SHS result in the dark and poor transparency to the naked eyes.

Fig.6. Absorption feature of PCD samples: a) absorption spectra in 0 – 3 THz range and b) absorption spectra in 5 – 7 THz range and c) analysis of fine fitted main characteristic absorption peak in a)

Fig.6 shows the absorption features of different PCD samples and analysis of the characteristic peak. It has been postulated that a high degree of lattice disorder such as in GB areas and/or mechanically generated defects in diamond would result in strong phonon excitation of vibration. For the hypothetical possible absorption from nitrogen in diamond, this common impurity is not effective in microwave range [21,40]. Likewise, the identical growth environment in terms of the possibility of nitrogen existence associated with the different absorption intensity can rule out the effect of nitrogen. In diamond with broad forbidden gap E_g the theoretical lower limit of intrinsic lattice loss (ILL) is determined by the multi-phonon absorption (MPA) in corresponding the ideal crystal of diamond [16]. At the THz range, where the frequency $\omega \ll \omega_D$ (Debye frequency of diamond, $2.43 \cdot 10^{14} \cdot s^{-1}$), the two-phonon process exists, i.e., excitation of one phonon of frequency ω_1 and absorption of one phonon of frequency ω_2 . While in the diamond crystal structure, the contacts of longitudinal optic and acoustic lattice vibration branches are at the two-dimensional areas on the Brillouin zone (BZ) boundaries. For the estimations of the ILL and theory of MPA, the dielectric loss of diamond is extremely low [16]. The main absorption for ultra-low loss diamond material is due to the included sp^2 phases. These graphitic carbon acts as an additional microwave absorber and increases the dielectric loss [25]. Therefore, imperfections in the CVD diamond may introduce the

THz response because phonon modes of diamond are IR-inactive, but sp^2 phases are active [26, 41].

Indeed, especially in 1–100 cm^{-1} (~ 0.1 –3 THz) the atomic vibrations are materials independent and carbon atoms in different sp^2 hybridization structure such as benzene and/or alkyl chain do mainly take part in the 0.1–3 THz absorption with different vibration modes [42–44]. As shown in Fig.6(a, c), the main characteristic absorption peak at ~ 2.88 THz ($\sim 96 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ or 11.9 meV) become stronger with the sp^2 content increase, corresponding to Fig.3 and Fig.4. From first principles of the key vibration modes in graphitic materials, it was determined that there is a strong excitation frequency of phonon branches at $\sim 95 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ [41]. The frequency of the out-of-plane acoustic phonon (ZA) mode of bilayer graphene (BLG) is at $\sim 95 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and the difference of twisted-BLG is found to be in the phonon frequency range 90–100 cm^{-1} depending on the phonon densities of states (DOS). This is resulted from the shifting of flexural ZA mode of BLG and twisted-BLG, which can be used for noncontact characterization of twisted bilayer or multilayer graphene (MLG) [45]. Also, the twisting-induced change in the van-der-Waals interlayer interactions weakly affects the phonon frequencies. Giura et al. [46] reminded the vibration of the atoms perpendicular to the plane is associated with the ZA branch. And in graphite (or MLG), this mode splits into a branch in which the two planes vibrate in phase, ZA , and a branch in which the planes antiphase, ZO' (out-of-plane transverse optical). This theoretical optical mode frequency in BLG is $\sim 80 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and can increase up to $\sim 114 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in graphite [46,47]. Oshima et al. [48] has experimentally reported the ZO of graphite at $\sim 95 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and Saha et al. [49] presented the optical phonon frequency of MLG at $\sim 96.7 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ by density-functional theory (DFT). Consequently, the main absorption characteristic peak at $\sim 96 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is considered as the attribution of the out-of-plane phonon vibration mode of sp^2 phases at GBs (and/or defects) of PCDs, e.g., graphene nanoribbon or graphite [15,39]. Furthermore, the FWHM (based on Lorentz fine fitting) of this characteristic peak (of which the FWHM is within the 2–11.6 cm^{-1} range of typical absorption of solids [5]) is widened with the narrowing of GBs associated with reduction of sp^2 proportion owing to the disordered graphitic phases resulting from less space generated heavier mismatch/defects at GBs. Likewise, owing to the superabundant graphitic phases or concomitant defects in BPCD-30-SHS, extra prominent absorption peaks of it at around 5–5.6 THz is overwhelming than that of other samples.

Meanwhile, a relative weaker peak of all the PCDs except BPCD-30-SHS exists at 0.2 THz position. Strong excitation of the lowest order longitudinal acoustic phonon mode is a feature of the dynamics in thinner graphite, on the order of $\sim 10 \text{ nm}$ [46]. However, owing to the possible thicker graphite resulting from larger GBs/pores space in BPCD-30-SHS, as shown in Fig.4(d) and Fig.5(b), this characteristic peak is weakened and it may also be previously suppressed by relative higher vibration noise of more disorders. Clearly, the whole baseline of BPCD-30-SHS is apparently higher than that of rest of PCDs owing to the worse quality. It should be mentioned that the bulge from 0.3–2.4 THz is due to the relative higher amorphous network resulting

from GBs and/or defects, which is expected to manifest relatively higher distorted sound-wave-like absorption baseline [42]. However, the more **extensive** cleavage of crystal, e.g., of WPCD-10-SHS shown in Fig.5(a), caused obvious swell at 2.0-2.7 THz and the slightly stronger absorption baseline at 5-7 THz in Fig.6(b) **are confirmed** by the absorption analysis of SHS polished SCD with large-scale uniform cleavage fault.

Besides, owing to the many phonon frequencies of sp^2 phases and/or defects located in the intermediate frequency range, 3–5 THz, the remarkable irregular absorption spectroscopy is located within this range. This shows good agreement with an obvious hump of pure graphite sheet in this waveband referring to the database of some common materials in THz range by FTIR-FIR [51]. Correspondingly, the jagged refractive index of PCDs in this waveband shows an obvious fluctuation, which indicates that some absorptions have made contribution to the sharp rise of dielectric loss. **Why the distinct delamination trend of spectrum of PCDs in the range higher than 3 THz must occur could be due to other unknown reasons.**

Fig.7. Refractive index (with errors in thick curves) and corresponding permittivity of PCDs from 0 – 7 THz.

Fig.7 shows the refractive index (n) of PCDs in 0.1–7 THz. The n has a dependence on the absorption (a) of the material, the related dielectric loss ϵ'' and on the free space wavelength λ_0 are in the relationship as displayed in Eq (1) [7, 52],

$$\epsilon'' = \frac{\alpha \cdot \lambda_0}{2\pi \cdot n} \quad (1)$$

The enhanced absorption corresponds to an obvious down-warping of n at ~ 2.88 THz position as shown in Fig.7, as well as the position at ~ 3.9 THz ($\sim 130 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\sim 16.1 \text{ meV}$) which is in good agreement with the theoretically calculated energy of the ZA mode at symmetry point Γ of graphitic phase [53,54]. The THz-TDS enables the determination of the complex permittivity ϵ of a material over the frequency 0.1–7 THz based on $n = \sqrt{\epsilon}$. Low dielectric loss of diamond allows ultra-low transmission loss of high-power high-frequency EMW. To understand the loss mechanism in diamond, the dielectric response $\epsilon = \epsilon' - i\epsilon''$, where ϵ' is the real part and ϵ'' the

imaginary part and the loss tangent $\tan \delta = \frac{\varepsilon''}{\varepsilon'}$ at high frequency in wide THz are imperative [50,55-57]. The dielectric loss of diamond mainly resulted from the following origins: electron polarization (or electric conduction), ILL of sp^2 phases and disorder, and wavelength dispersion of Rayleigh scattering.

The electron polarization is dominant in diamond associated with sp^2 impurities because the dipolar and ionic polarization are negligible in diamond and the localized electrons of sp^3 atomic orbitals suppress the electronic polarization [55,57]. The dielectric constant can be expressed as $\varepsilon = \chi_e + I$ where χ_e is the electron polarization coefficient, which depends on the grain size and the bandgap expansion ($\Delta E_g/E_g$). Here E_g is the bandgap and its expansion can cause the decrease of the static dielectric constant, which results from the surface bond concentration and the increase of surface-to-volume ratio of crystal grains [57]. These two factors are enhanced with the deterioration of PCD quality, as shown in Fig.4 and Fig.5. This mechanism was experimentally proved by the decrease of permittivity of porous diamond films associated with a rising proportion of graphite [55].

Furthermore, the main loss of PCD at MM waves is believed to be due to extrinsic conductivity, which **has an inverse frequency dependence**, $\tan \delta \propto 1/f$. However, Garin [58] and Mocheneva [59] found that it is impossible to extract the pure $1/f$ dependence. The concentration of shallow levels, especially the extremely shallow levels (meV) induced by native defects and/or sp^2 -like atoms located at GBs with dangling bonds, is significantly higher in poor quality diamond, which results in a monotonous decrease of the permittivity with frequency increasing [60,61]. They also proposed that a scattering mechanism exists over 0.2 THz, which results in the *tan tan* δ growth. **However, in** addition to the proposed **scattering caused** by GBs or defects, owing to the basically constant refractive index in 0.1–3 THz waveband, as shown in Fig.7, we consider that the effect of ILL of impurities and/or defects, e.g., the absorption at 0.2 and 2.88 THz as well as the disordered sound-wave-like absorption bulge starting at nearly 1.0 THz shown in Fig.6(a), plays a non-negligible, or even a more important role in this materials independent range. **Also, as** shown clearly in Fig.7, in this frequency band, the permittivity of all the PCDs exhibit local reduction corresponding to the absorption positions, while the permittivity is constant at around 5.76 ± 0.2 which is shown as yellow area. The slightly higher refractive index n of poor-quality (BPCD-300-SHS) is due to the relative higher amorphous diamond (*a*-D, of which the ε was confirmed to be ~ 6 at low energy range [50]) resulting from GBs and artificial defects although the disorder is expected to manifest relatively higher absorption baseline which may cause whole weak decline of n .

Clearly, the loss trends are strongly dependent on the quality of diamond. As illustrated in Eq (2), in addition to the first term in the formula describing the sp^2 phases causing **electrical conduction** loss, the f dependence of second term is different. It would be proportional to f if the loss is from the ILL of phonon vibration, and to f^3 if it is from scattering of GBs or heavy defects [21, 25].

$$\tan \delta = \frac{a}{f} + bf^n \quad 1 \leq n \leq 3 \quad (2)$$

where a is a parameter related to electrical conductivity and dielectric permittivity, and b the density of defects. Komiyama [62] reported a drastic transmittance decrease of an a -D film as f increases in low terahertz range; and Yamamoto et al [26] presented an obvious increase in loss and predicted additional dielectric response at higher f . In Fig.7, the intermediate frequency band, i.e., from 3–5 THz, is more ‘sensitive’ to the sp^2 impurities and defects owing to the multiple absorption in wide range resulting from the anisotropy of graphitic carbon structure and disordered state of defects, which result in disordered fluctuations of refractive index. Corresponding to the factor b in Eq.(2), which is a coefficient proportional to density of defects, it can drastically increase the dielectric loss at certain f if the density of defects is prominent. This is the one reason why the refractive index of PCDs with different quality is clearly divided in 3–5 THz range. However, more importantly, the n decreases trend as f increases is not due to the fixed absorption frequency but due to the scattering effects, of which the strength is proportional to f^4 [62]. As the f increases, the wavelength narrows down to the grains or pores dimension-comparable range, the mean free path decreases rapidly and diffusive EMW propagation with multiple scattering becomes dominant. Scherer [25] pointed out a loss term due to the scattering by defects or GBs, and this effect was confirmed by other researchers using PCDs [21,25,38]. It is considered that its loss may be expressed as

$$\tan \delta \propto d^6 f^4 \quad (3)$$

where d and f are average size of defects and frequency, respectively. Meanwhile, it can be shown that the loss tangent can be expressed as [52]:

$$\tan \delta = \frac{2\gamma}{k \cdot n} \quad (4)$$

where k is wave number, n is refractive of diamond and γ is given by Eq. (5) [52]:

$$\gamma = \frac{k^4}{6\pi} \cdot \frac{(\varepsilon-1)^2 N V^2}{(\varepsilon+L(\varepsilon-1))^2} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{2}{3}(\beta-1) + \frac{1}{3}(\beta+1)^2\right) \quad (5)$$

where N and V are scatters density and volume in diamond plate, L is a geometry factor related to spheroid long axes and β is the parameter equal to ratio between spheroid polarizability tensor components in main axes.

As for the effect of concomitant pores between grains as shown in Fig.4 and Fig.5(b), it can be used as a two-phase dielectric mixing model, the Maxwell-Garnett model, based in Rayleigh mixing formula:

$$(\varepsilon_m - \varepsilon_p)/(\varepsilon_m + 2\varepsilon_p) = (I - P) \times [(\varepsilon_d - \varepsilon_p)/(\varepsilon_d + 2\varepsilon_p)] \quad (6)$$

where the porosity (P) is the volumetric fraction of pores in the composite dielectric, ε_m is the permittivity of the equivalent dielectric mixture, and ε_d and ε_p are the permittivities of diamond and pores, respectively [57]. It can be concluded that the dielectric constant of PCD with pores decrease monotonically with the increase of its porosity. Certainly, many pores or GBs are in the order of tens microns as displayed in Fig.5, such structures are comparable to THz wavelength, especially less than 100 μm , i.e., higher than 3 THz (100 cm^{-1}), and therefore cause frequency-dependent

volume scattering as mentioned. Indeed, the Mie scattering coefficient (α_M) presenting as $\alpha_M = \pi \rho e_\lambda l^2$ would be skyrocketed exponentially. **Instead, Rayleigh scattering** (displaying as $\alpha_R = \frac{N \omega^4 a}{16 \pi c^4}$, of which the N is the number of small scattering center and the a is the attenuation coefficient) **plays a dominant role**, if the size of scattering center (l) is close to the wavelength (λ) in the range of micron magnitude [63].

Therefore, the dielectric loss is surged by rising f if the GBs and pores density are dominating, which means the quality of the diamond has deteriorated. This gives rise to the dramatically dropping of n , namely, obvious degradation of dielectric properties as shown in Fig.7. As illustrated, the overall n of WPCD-10-SHS is basically at around 2.4 although some losses occurred in 3–5 THz owing to the inevitable absorption of sp^2 phases and defects, as well as possible weak scattering of thin GBs. In summary, apart from the f dependent loss caused by free charge carriers and not distinctly divided absorption spectra in most ranges shown in Fig.6(b), we deduced that the main dielectric loss mechanism of PCD films in higher THz range (i.e., 3–7 THz) is scattering, which is enhanced by extended GBs and concomitant pores. In order to strongly support the deduction of absorptions and dielectric loss mechanism in wide frequency waveband, high quality SCD films with various degrees of artificial defects, especially the wide-range GB-like cleavage fault were radiated as well.

Fig.8. CL images of artificial defect topography of SCD samples: a) SCD-UP; b) SCD-MS; c) SCD-HS; d) SCD-SHS. The inset in each image is the corresponding fine fitted Raman spectra

Fig.9. AFM images and surface roughness of a) unpolished (SCD-UP) and b) polished (SCD-SHS)

As mentioned earlier, high quality diamond would be the best choice as an EMW transmission material especially for SCD which are without GBs. Sustained and rapid progress of CVD technology has made the high quality SCD in large size possible. Fig.8 shows CL images together with Raman spectra of four SCDs, which are originally the same that from a large high-quality mother free-standing film, with different degree of purposely produced defects. As clearly displayed, from unpolished SCD-UP to heavily polished SCD-SHS, the defects extended gradually from basically damage free to partial damage and then to totally cleavage fault [31]. Correspondingly, the Raman spectra show that the sp^2 phase was generated increasingly from the totally sp^2 -free of SCD-UP (in which the appearing of the conformed sp^2 related peak in THz absorption spectra, is due to the extremely high sensitivity of THz spectroscopy than Raman spectroscopy [11]). Especially in Fig.8(d), the crystal is uniformly damaged along with (111) cleavage plane associated with apparently proliferated sp^2 as well as wider FWHM of sp^3 peak. As shown in Fig.9(a), the SCD-UP, the surface roughness RMS is 10.32 nm, however, the ultra-smooth surface of those polished samples after 3D-DFP can be obtained, e.g., the roughness of SCD-SHS is in RMS of 0.17 nm in Fig9(b) [31].

Fig.10. Absorption feature of SCD samples: a) absorption spectra in 0 – 3 THz range and b) absorption spectra in 5 – 7 THz range and c) analysis of characteristic absorption peak in a)

Fig.10 shows the absorption features and fitting analysis of the characteristic peak of SCDs. The surface diffuse scattering effect of rough SCD-UP results in relative higher absorption noise baseline. Yamada et al [20] has discussed that a good SCD surface quality and thickness homogeneity can improve the transmission property. This also has been confirmed and it generated dielectric loss will be presented in the refractive index measurement because the RMS surface height will cause significant scattering based on the Fraunhofer Criterion [20,64]. For the SCD-MS, the spectrum is a horizontal line with basically no absorption except the weak sp^2 phonon characteristic peak at 2.88 THz. This is owing to the inevitable defect, as shown in Fig.8(b), resulting from growth and/or 3D-DFP process. After HS polishing, defects in SCD-HS was extended as shown in Fig.8(c). This change gives rise to the higher absorption intensity and larger FWHM of sp^2 related peak as displayed in Fig.10(c). Meanwhile, there is a weak bulge at 2.2-2.7 THz that maybe due to the damage/cleavage caused phonon noise, which is similar with that in WPCD-10-SHS as shown in Fig.6(a). Indeed, furthermore, for SCD-SHS, the further ballooned (2.0-2.7 THz) and left-shifted bulge associated with the distinctly widened sp^2 related phonon vibration peak, are all engendered by the heavy tile-roof-like cleavage.

In addition, as analyzed in Fig.10(c), the FWHM of sp^2 related peak of SCD-UP is merely around 0.02 THz (0.7 cm⁻¹). This is because that the inevitable grown defects (or dislocation), **which did not deteriorate**: however, the surface roughness, causing higher absorption noise baseline, elevated the weak peak. In Fig.10(b), the defects

causing additional wide absorptions in 5-7 THz band are mainly located at around 5.0-5.6 THz and 6.0-6.8 THz, which are also similar with the weak bulge displayed in Fig.6(b) (maybe somewhat enveloped by the noise from multi-directional GBs).

Fig.11. Refractive index (with errors in thick curves) of SCD samples from 0 – 7 THz

Further investigation of refractive index of SCDs with variable designedly artificial defects were collected in Fig.11 to consolidate the surface quality effect and dielectric loss mechanism. Indeed, the rough surface makes a negative effect on n (or permittivity), although there is no mechanical force generated defects. Consequently, in low-frequency range, the n of SCD-UP is ~ 2.35 , which is lower than that of other SCDs owing to the higher absorption baseline. With the **increasing frequency**, the n of SCD-UP is merely equal to that of SCD-HS, which has obvious partial damage shown in Fig.8(c). As displayed the n of SCD-MS, it shows relative constant in 0-7 THz full range without clear dielectric loss and obvious frequency dependence, owing to the less defects in bulk after MS polishing. While the bulk diamond with partial defects after HS polishing, the limited electron polarization of localized sp^2 and weak absorption basically have not produced losses in THz low- f range. In intermediate and high frequency band, **however**, the defects begin to significantly **show** the effect on the losses, the phonon vibration absorption and stronger scattering of defects in these wavebands. **In particular, this results** in un-negligible dielectric loss. Especially for the SCD-SHS with heavy wavelength-equivalent GB-like cleavage fault, in addition to the strong absorption caused cliff-like drop of n at ~ 2.88 THz, the similar trend of ϵ results as PCDs especially the BPCD-30-SHS with Rayleigh scattering resulting from GB networks and pores together explains the very dramatic reduction in the permittivity. Similarly, the cleavage in clone mosaic SCD film also enhanced the dielectric loss in sub-THz range that have been given [20].

In summary, in low- f range where the atomic vibrations are material-independent, two fingerprint peaks of sp^2 phases located at ~ 0.2 and 2.88 THz are confirmed. Consequently, the cleavages and GBs have no obvious impact on the permittivity loss in the low- f range. However, large-scale defects, e.g., GBs and cleavage faults, result in disordered sound waves resembled absorption noise as well as overall decline of

permittivity. Furthermore, in ‘defects-active’ medium and high THz waveband, other sp^2 or defects related phonon absorption, e.g., 3.9 THz, together with stronger scattering effect of defects e.g., GBs (GB-like cleavage) and pores result in un-negligible dielectric loss. Therefore, overall, it could be expected that defects-free higher quality SCD film will not generate intrinsic dielectric loss in wide THz range and can meet the requirements of advanced THz technology application, i.e., window material especially in harsh environment. In return, for diamond ultra-sensitive quality diagnose, the THz-TDS is considered as a powerful and effective approach. Practically, concerning the better cost-performance and availability, a large grain high quality PCD with thin GBs may fulfill the performance requirement in certain frequency range. These findings can be act as references to promote the THz spectroscopy to be a hyperfine tool to identify diamond quality for advanced high-tech applications in the future.

Conclusion

An insight of several significant responses of diamond in wide THz waveband was investigated in depth using 0 - 7 THz-TDS on a range of systematically synthesized and processed diamond films. Two conspicuous fingerprint absorption peaks located at about 0.2 and 2.88 THz in materials-independent waveband (i.e., low frequency range 0.1-3THz) as well as one position at 3.9 THz in intermediate waveband (3-5 THz) are attributed to the sp^2 vibration modes of as-growth graphitic phases at GBs and/or defects in bulk crystal. Correspondingly, in low frequency range, the discrimination of permittivity of different diamonds is not obvious and the dielectric loss mainly results from absorptions. However, in the intermediate- and high (5-7 THz) frequency range, in addition to the absorption of defects and sp^2 phases, the electronic polarization of increased sp^2 and especially the scattering effect, resulting from wavelength-equivalent grains and/or pores, begin to make important contributions to the dielectric loss and play an increasing trend depending on the development of defects, e.g., the extended GBs and/or GB-like cleavage faults. For the un-ultra-smooth surface, however, an enhancement of absorption baseline and dielectric loss is found. Overall, it is shown that a diamond film with lower defects density and precise surface preparation is the ideal transmission material in wide THz waveband. At the same time, THz frequency wave also provides a powerful hyperfine quality discrimination tool for diamond films for advanced technological applications.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported by the National Key Research and Development Program of China (No.2016YFE0133200) and European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Staff Exchange Scheme (No.734578). Special thanks to the national high-level university-sponsored graduate program of China Scholarship Council (CSC).

References

- [1] P.U. Jepsen D.G. Cooke M. Koch, *Laser Photon. Rev.* **2011**, 5, 124.
- [2] H.J. Song, T. Nagatsuma, *IEEE Trans. THz Sci. Technol.* **2011**, 1, 256.
- [3] R.M. Smith, M.A. Arnold, *Appl. Spectrosc. Rev.* **2011**, 46, 636.
- [4] A.R. Sanchez, X.C. Zhang, *IEEE J. Sel. Top. Quan.* **2008**, 14, 260.
- [5] S. Terentyev, V. Blank, T. Kolodziej, Y. Shvydko, *Rev. Sci. Instrum.* **2016**, 87, 125117.
- [6] K. Sakamoto, A. Kasugai, M. Tsuneoka, K. Takahashi, T. Imai, T. Kariya, Y. Mitsunala, *Rev. Sci. Instrum.* **1999**, 70, 208.
- [7] J. Chamberlain, M.N. Afsar, D.K. Murray, G.D. Price, A.S. Zafar, *IEEE Trans. Instrum. Mea.* **1974**, 12, 483.
- [8] I.F. Akyildiz, J.M. Jornet, C. Hana, *Phys. Commun.* **2014**, 12, 16.
- [9] S. Koenig, D. Lopez-Diaz, J. Antes, F. Boes, R. Henneberger, A. Leuther, A. Tessmann, R. Schmogrow, D. Hillerkuss, R. Palmer, T. Zwick, C. Koos, W. Freude, O. Ambacher, J. Leuthold, I. Kallfass, *Nat. Photon.* **2013**, 7, 977.
- [10] J.E. Haddad, B. Bousquet, L. Canioni, P. Mounaix, *Trac-trend. Anal. Chem.* **2013**, 44, 98
- [11] H.H. Mantsch, D. Naumann, *J. Mol. Struct.* **2010**, 964, 1.
- [12] J. Sibik, J.A. Zeitler, *Adv. Drug. Deliver. Rev.* **2016**, 100, 147.
- [13] A. Taschin, P. Bartolini, J. Tasseva, R. Torre, *Measurement* **2018**, 118, 282.
- [14] R. Heidinger, G. Dammertz, A. Meier, M.K. Thumm, *IEEE Trans. Plasma. Sci.* **2002**, 30, 800.
- [15] R.S. Sussmann, CVD Diamond for Electronic Devices and Sensors. John Wiley & Sons, Germany **2009**.
- [16] B.M. Garin, presented at *IEEE 12th Inter. Conf. Terahertz Electro.* **2004**, 9-10, 1422127.
- [17] M. Schwander, K. Partes, *Diam. Relat. Mater.* **2011**, 20, 1287.
- [18] G. Chen, B. Li, H. Li, H. Lan, F. Dai, Q. Xue, X. Han, L. Hei, J. Song, C. Li, *Diam. Relat. Mater.* **2010**, 19, 1078.
- [19] J.M.L. Floch, R. Bara, J.G. Hartnett, M.E. Tobar, D. Mouneyrac, D. Passerieux, D. Cros, J. Krupka, P. Goy, S. Caroopen, *J. Appl. Phys.* **2011**, 109, 094103.
- [20] H. Yamada, A. Meier, F. Mazzocchi, S. Schreck, T. Scherer, *Diam. Relat. Mater.* **2015**, 58, 1.
- [21] Y. Liu, M. Ding, J. Su, Y. Li, P. Zhang, X. Lu, W. Tang, *Diam. Relat. Mater.* **2017**, 76, 68.
- [22] B.M. Grain, V.V. Parshin, S.E. Myasnikova, V.G. Ralchenko, *Diam. Relat. Mater.* **2003**, 12, 1755.
- [23] V.I. Polyakova, A.I. Rukovishnikov, B.M. Garin, L.A. Avdeeva, R. Heidinger, V.V. Parshin, V.G. Ralchenko, *Diam. Relat. Mater.* **2005**, 14, 604.
- [24] F. Mazzocchi, S. Schreck, D. Strauss, G. Aiello, A. Meier, T. Scherer, *Fusion. Eng. Des.* **2017**, 123, 820.
- [25] T.A. Scherer, D. Strauss, A. Meier, Y. Mathis, V. Judin, W.M. Sebert, W. Smirnov, C.E. Nebel, *MRS Proceedings*, **2011**, 1282, 177.
- [26] K. Yamamoto, H. Iwasaki, S. Tsuji, R. Yasuda, K. Fukui, M. Tani, T. Shimozuma, S. Ito, T. Saito, presented at *IEEE 37th Inter. Conf. Infrared, Millimeter, Terahertz Waves*, **2012**, 9, 6380244.
- [27] V.V. Kubarev, *Nucl. Instrum. Meth. A*, **2009**, 603, 22.
- [28] V.V. Kubarev, presented at *IEEE 32nd Inter. Conf. Infrared, Millimeter Waves*, **2007**, 9 4516767
- [29] G. Chen, B. Li, Z. Yan, F. Lu, *Diam. Relat. Mater.* **2012**, 21, 83.

- [30] L.F. Hei, J. Liu, C.M. Li, J.H. Song, W.Z. Tang, F.X. Lu, *Diam. Relat. Mater.* **2012**, *30*, 77.
- [31] Y.T. Zheng, H.T. Ye, R. Thornton, T.J. Ochalski, J.L. Liu, J. Wang, A. Cumont, R.Y. Zhang, J.J. Wei, L.X. Chen, C.M. Li, *Diam. Relat. Mater.* **2020**, *101*, 107600.
- [32] O. Sushko, PhD thesis, Queen Mary Univ London, **2014**.
- [33] J.R. Rabeau, P. John, J.I.B. Wilson, Y. Fan, *J. Appl. Phys.* **2004**, *96*, 6724.
- [34] K.J. Sankaran, K. Srinivasu, H.C. Chen, C.L. Dong, K.C. Leou, C.Y. Lee, N.H. Tai, I.N. Lin, *J. Appl. Phys.* **2013**, *114*, 054304
- [35] S.J. Harris, A.M. Weiner, *J. Appl. Phys.* **1990**, *67*, 6520.
- [36] A.C. Ferrari, J. Robertson, *Phil. Trans. R. Soc. Lond. A* **2004**, *362*, 2477–2512,
- [37] B.V. Crist, *J. Electron. Spectrosc. Relat. Phenom.* **2019**, *231*, 75.
- [38] Y. Liu, M. Ding, J.J. Su, H. Ren, X.R. Lu, W. Tang, *Diam. Relat. Mater.* **2017**, *73*, 114.
- [39] X.J. Hu, C.K. Chen, S.H. Lu, *Carbon* **2016**, *98*, 671.
- [40] M.H. Ding, Y.Q. Liu, X.R. Lu, Y.F. Li, W.Z. Tang, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **2019**, *114*, 162901.
- [41] N. Bonini, M. Lazzeri, N. Marzari, F. Mauri, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **2007**, *99*, 176802.
- [42] S.N. Taraskin, S.I. Simdyankin, S.R. Elliott, J.R. Neilson, T. Lo, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **2006**, *97*, 055504.
- [43] Z.Z. Chen, Y.R. Jiang, L.L. Jiang, H. Ma, *Spectrochim. Acta. A*, **2016**, *153*, 741.
- [44] T. Morimoto, T. Miyamoto, H. Yamakawa, T. Terashige, T. Ono, N. Kida, H. Okamoto, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **2017**, *118*, 107602.
- [45] A.I. Cocemasov, D.L. Nika, A.A. Balandin, *Phys. Rev. B* **2013**, *88*, 035428.
- [46] P. Giura, N. Bonini, G. Creff, J. B. Brubach, P. Roy, M. Lazzeri, *Phys. Rev. B* **2012**, *86*, 121404(R)
- [47] R.P. Chatelain, V.R. Morrison, B.L.M. Klarenaar, B.J. Siwick, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **2014**, *113*, 235502.
- [48] C. Oshima, T. Aizawa, R. Souda, Y. Ishizawa, Y. Sumiyoshi, *Solid State Commun.* **1988**, *65*, 1601.
- [49] S.K. Saha, U.V. Waghmare, H.R. Krishnamurthy, A.K. Sood, *Phys. Rev. B* **2008**, *78*, 165421.
- [50] F.L. Xiong, Y. Y. Wang, R. P. H. Chang, *Phys. Rev. B* **1993**, *48*, 8016.
- [51] <http://thzdb.org/index.php?name=Graphite&word=&sc=2829>
- [52] A. Scheuring, P. Probst, A. Stockhausen, K. Ilin, M. Siegel, T. A. Scherer, A. Meier, D. Strauss, presented at *IEEE 35th Inter. Conf. Infrared, Millimeter, Terahertz Waves*, **2010**, *9*, 5612543.
- [53] R. Nicklow, N. Wakabayashi, H.G. Smith, *Phys. Rev. B* **1972**, *5*, 4951.
- [54] L. Vitali, M. A. Schneider, K. Kern, *Phys. Rev. B* **2004**, *69*, 121414.
- [55] H. Sakaue, N. Yoshimura, S. Shingubara, T. Takahagi, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **2003**, *83*, 2226
- [56] R. Peretti, S. Mityukovskiy, K. Froberger, M.A. Mebarki, S. Eliet, M. Vanwollegem, J.F. Lampin, *IEEE Trans. THz Sci. Technol.* **2019**, *9*, 136.
- [57] Z.L. Wang, J.J. Li, Z.H. Sun, Y.L. Li, Q. Luo, C.Z. Gu, Z. Cui, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **2007**, *90*, 133118.
- [58] B.M. Garin, V.V. Parshin, V.I. Polyakov, A.I. Rukovishnikov, E.A. Serov, O.S. Mocheneva, C.C. Jia, W.Z. Tang, F.X. Lu, Recent Advances in Broadband Dielectric Spectroscopy, Springer, **2013**, pp. 79–87.
- [59] O.S. Mocheneva, V.V. Parshin, *Radiophys. Quant. El.* **2007**, *50*, 946.
- [60] B.M. Garin, V.I. Polyakov, A.I. Rukovishnikov, L.A. Avdeeva, V.N. Derkach, V.V. Parshin, V.G. Ralchenko, *Diam. Relat. Mater.* **2006**, *15*, 1917.

- [61] P. Zapol, M. Sternberg, L.A. Curtiss, T. Frauenheim, D.M. Gruen, *Phys. Rev. B* **2001**, *65*, 045403
- [62] Y. Komiyama, H. Abe, Y. Kamimura, K. Edagawa, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **2016**, *108*, 191110.
- [63] K.-E. Peiponen, J.A. Zeitler, M. Kuwata-Gonokami, *Terahertz spectroscopy and imaging*, Springer, Germany, **2013**.
- [64] S. Schecklman, L.M. Zurk, S. Henry, G.P. Kniffin, *J. Appl. Phys.* **2011**, *109*, 094902.